

Digital assets
and tools
**for circular
value chains and
manufacturing
products**

15 Partners

10 Countries

5.99M Total Budget

42 Months

Funded by
the European Union

**3 EU demo critical
value chains**

**3 production
environments**

**Didactic Factories
deployment at RTOs**

The Project

DaCapo aims at the creation of human-centric digital tools and services to facilitate the adoption of Circular Economy (CE) strategies across manufacturing value chains and products lifecycle.

These tools and services, focused on the introduction of new digital assets, AI-based systems and the application of process and product Digital Twins improve the sustainability and efficiency of imported and critical raw materials in manufacturing.

A RAMI 4.0- compliant digital platform

A newly conceptualized Digital Product Passport (DPP)

A digital pipeline based on a Modular Digital Thread concept

Realistic Digital Twins (DT) for products and processes

A Circular Economy Decision Support System (CE-DSS) as the key knowledge backbone

Product-centric management and eco-design approaches

Sustainable manufacturing strategies at shopfloor level

Advanced diagnostic tools and improved predictive maintenance strategies

Use Cases

DaCapo will demonstrate its commercial and replicability potential on high-impact applications in critical EU manufacturing sectors

Aeronautics

Extending sustainable manufacturing and reparability approaches for aeronautic value chains.

ICT & consumer electronics

Eco-design, diagnosis and maintenance for modular mobile phones.

FAIRPHONE

Warehousing

R-cycles in material flows for warehouse design, construction and operation.

PESMEL

Consortium

The DaCapo consortium consists of 15 partners from 10 European countries:

- 8 RTOs
- 4 large companies
- 2 SMEs
- 1 European Association

TNO FAIRPHONE

Scuola universitaria professionale
della Svizzera italiana

SUPSI

aimen
CENTRO TECNOLOGICO - TECHNOLOGY CENTRE

PESMEL

GKN AEROSPACE

PACE

INTERNATIONAL DATA SPACES ASSOCIATION

POLITECNICO MILANO 1863

UNIMORE
UNIVERSITÀ DEGLI STUDI DI MODENA E REGGIO EMILIA

ENGINEERING
THE DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION COMPANY

core
Engineering Industry 4.0

LMS
Laboratory for Manufacturing Systems & Automation

core|IC

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